

THE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH GROUP ON WOOD PROTECTION

Section 5

Sustainability and Environment

**Reviewing material intensities, technologies, characteristics, product
and building design with underutilised wood in HORIZON project
WoodStock**

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ABSTRACT

The Horizon Europe project WoodStock develops climate-smart solutions to increase the use of underutilised wood in the European construction sector. Through a Living Lab approach, and in support of the New European Bauhaus (NEB), the 4-year project promotes sustainable wood construction practices and advances the circular economy. This paper presents the WoodStock definition of the four underutilised wood streams and highlights six WoodStock deliverables of interest to the IRG community: D3.2 Material intensities in the building stock, D5.1 Review of new technologies and processes, D5.2 Characteristics of underutilised wood stocks, D5.3 Review of zero-waste product concepts, D5.4 Review of zero-waste building concepts, D8.1 International Survey.

Keywords: circular, zero-waste, underutilized wood resources, material flow analysis, dynamic LCA, carbon storage, Living Labs, NEB

1. PROJECT OVERVIEW

The Horizon Europe project WoodStock develops climate-smart solutions to increase the use of underutilised wood in the European construction sector. Through a Living Lab approach, and in support of the New European Bauhaus (NEB), the 4-year project promotes sustainable wood construction practices and advances the circular economy. It runs from 1 November 2024 to 31 October 2028. The WoodStock project consists of 12 European partners (InnoRenew merged with the University of Primorska), and is coordinated by Ghent University. The consortium includes research institutes, universities, umbrella organisations from the wood sector, and small SMEs (Fig. 1). More information can be found on our website: <https://www.woodstockproject.eu/>

Figure 1: WoodStock consortium of 12 partners, with indication of the 6 Living Labs.

1.1 WoodStock ambitions

- quantify and map wood resources through material flows, carbon accounting, and a robust dynamic Life Cycle Assessment (d-LCA) method: resources, flows and impacts
- develop zero-waste, circular product and building designs that consider human health and well-being: zero-waste solutions for healthy living
- provide holistic policy, innovation, and business strategy frameworks: innovation, policies, and strategies
- establish a European Wood Construction Observatory and NEB Lab

1.2 Concept

The core methodology of the WoodStock project (Fig. 2) uses a **transdisciplinary and multi-actor LL approach** within the **framework of the NEB compass**. The NEB framework addresses climate-smart solutions in a holistic and innovative manner, by promoting a multidisciplinary approach centered around NEB values and working principles. Our six LLs offer a dynamic space for the co-creation, exploration, and implementation of innovative and sustainable solutions based on NEB principles. Our methodological approach consists of 3 main **themes**, all feeding into the European Wood Construction Observatory (EWCO): (1) Modelling the supply-demand of under-utilized resources and assessing the carbon impact; (2) Circular strategies and zero-waste solutions for a healthy living environment; (3) Advancing policy, businesses, and standards for a sustainable wood construction.

Figure 2: WoodStock methodology

2. CLASSIFICATION OF UNDERUTILISED WOOD STOCKS

WoodStock has described **four main categories** of underutilised wood, based on EU classifications (Fig. 3). These materials are often overlooked in conventional supply chains but hold significant potential for use in construction. By valorising these resources, WoodStock aims to extend the lifespan of materials that would otherwise go to waste or be used in less durable applications.

2.1 Underutilised hardwood

Hardwoods are angiosperm (flowering) trees, anatomically distinguished from softwoods (gymnosperms) by the presence of vessel. Despite diverse material characteristics, hardwoods remain underutilised in the construction industry. Common challenges such as limited stem yield, anatomical complexity, dimensional stability, varied wood properties, processing limitations, and lack of design standards affect their broader application. However, increased silvicultural diversity and availability, paired with promising high strength and stiffness values and novel processing techniques, present a significant opportunity for its use in sustainable, high-performance building applications.

2.2 Underutilised damaged wood

Wood originating from softwood and hardwood trees compromised by biotic agents (e.g., insect infestations, invasive species), abiotic events (e.g., storms, landslides, volcanic activity, droughts, floods), or wildfires, often lead to structural, aesthetic, and harvesting challenges. These concerns typically relegate it to low value uses such as bioenergy or low-grade timber. Yet, the rising frequency of climate-induced disturbances is increasing its availability. Moreover, if harvested at the appropriate time, processing and logistical challenges can be effectively managed, ensuring that the salvaged wood's mechanical properties are retained, making it valuable for higher-value applications.

2.3 Underutilised low-quality wood

Wood derived from harvesting residues such as branches, tops, stumps, thinning, or small-diameter wood, landscaping practices, roadside clearing as well as timber graded with low mechanical properties and limited structural application. Technical and logistical challenges

include high variability, a lack of performance data, and difficulty in processing. However, circular economy strategies and emerging data on strength-to-weight ratios suggest that certain stocks can match the mechanical performance of final-felling timber. This supports their scalable use in durable construction products, including both bespoke elements leveraging material variability and standardised outputs from heterogeneous inputs.

2.4 Underutilised post-consumer wood and residual wood

Wood recovered from construction and demolition activities, discarded products (e.g., pallets, furniture, demolition debris), manufacturing byproducts (e.g., offcuts, sawdust), or surplus stock. These stocks are commonly downcycled, used for bioenergy or landfilled due to contamination, inconsistent size and quality, high sorting costs, and lack of harmonised regulations. These technical, logistical, and legislative challenges obscure its potential. However, advances in sorting technologies and processing techniques enable higher-value reuse opportunities, offering substantial carbon savings and aligning with circular economy and cascade use principles.

Figure 3: Description of the four underutilised wood stocks based on their characteristics, challenges and potential

3. DELIVERABLES

The WoodStock project has advanced substantially, and to demonstrate this progress, several completed deliverables of particular relevance to the IRG community are highlighted. These deliverables will be published on the WoodStock Zenodo community and the Woodstock website after review by the European Commission.

3.1 Material intensities in the building stock

This deliverable reviews current European literature on material intensities with a specific focus on wood in the building stock. Urban mining—recovering materials from existing buildings—relies on understanding what materials are available. Material intensities (mass per floor area or per building volume) are a common way to estimate these stocks across building types and construction cohorts. The report maps the size and composition of the European building stock, compares wood intensity values across regions, building types, and construction periods, and summarises wood use in different building elements (Fig. 4). These findings provide the basis for subsequent analyses in the WoodStock project, including dynamic material flow modelling to estimate how much wood is stored in, entering, and leaving the European built environment.

Figure 4: Classification of building elements, parts, and wood types by building type, main construction material, load-bearing system, construction period, region, and element type (structural or non-structural).

3.2 Review of new technologies and processes

This review focuses on technologies and innovations that are currently being utilised in the timber construction sector globally. Through a combination of case study analysis and literature review, the objective is to define the most prominent technologies, categorise them into areas of use and showcase how they can be applied to increase the use of underutilised wood stocks in order to reduce waste consumption. This report reviewed 78 technologies and organised them along six phases in the timber construction cycle: identify, retrieve, catalogue, design, fabricate, and track (Fig 5). The technologies span various technology areas, covered by the following umbrella terms: scanning, data analytics and AI, data storage, tagging systems, software solutions, automated tools, primary raw-material processing, and the networks that connect these processes. The review shows that many suitable technologies are already available that can enable the use of underutilised wood stocks across all six phases. The technologies reviewed addressed conventional timber processing

but also identified gaps where the authors were unable to find examples of technologies being used for certain underutilised sources.

Figure 5: 6 Phases of technology – Divided by primary raw material (PRM) and as a post-consumer wood (PCW). Adapted from D5 workflow (De Wolf *et al.* 2024).

3.3 Characteristics of underutilised wood stocks

The objective of this study was to define, identify, characterise and derive potential applications for underutilised wood stocks in the EU, focusing on four underutilised wood stocks: hardwood, low-quality wood, damaged wood, and post-consumer and residual wood. Underutilised wood refers to woody biomass that remains outside higher-value applications, despite technical characteristics, ecological limits, and market conditions permitting its mobilisation. As depicted in Figure 6, this study articulates the concept through three complementary aspects: (i) abundance relative to sustainable harvest potential; (ii) limited allocation in current markets; and

(iii) cascade position with a credible pathway for higher value application. In this context, ‘higher value’ denotes applications that maximise the material’s potential in long-lived building products or components, with the possibility for further cascading utilisation.

The analysis compiles literature and statistics from some of the WoodStock partner countries: Finland, Norway, Belgium, the Netherlands, Poland, and Slovenia to assess material characteristics, and identify key resources. In doing so, the study contributes to the growing knowledge base on underutilised wood and its possible application in the built environment. The characterisation stage consolidates geometry/size attributes, mechanical and physical properties, and processability into design-relevant ranges for 22 varieties of wood stocks. The synthesis assembles stiffness, strength, hardness, density, durability, and dimensional-stability distributions at MC 12% and links these distributions to process routes advanced sorting and grading, moisture conditioning and drying schedules, machining and joinery requirements, and targeted modification or preservation so property profiles translate into manufacturable building materials. Importantly, characterisation compiles evidence from prior European studies and best practices to show that application routes have already been explored and that credible performance baselines exist, which strengthens the case for mobilisation beyond concept stage.

Figure 6: The three concepts on which underutilised wood is defined.

3.4 Review of zero-waste product concepts

This review assessed the socio-economic and environmental sustainability potential of building components developed from underutilised wood streams, analysed through the lens of the New European Bauhaus (NEB). Four categories were considered: low-quality wood, damaged wood, post-consumer and residual wood, and hardwoods. Their applications and the design strategies enabling their use were examined in terms of their broader sustainability implications.

More than 150 products were identified from academic and practice-based sources to map the current landscape of building components derived from these wood streams (Table 1). Products were categorised by geometry to align with architectural and structural logics, allowing an overview across scales and functions. From this survey, 17 case studies were selected for detailed analysis. These case studies represent projects and products that reach higher Ambition levels with respect to the NEB compass and were chosen to illustrate current possibilities and provide inspiration and guidance for future development. The findings highlighted the need to strengthen the emphasis on the socio-economic dimensions of sustainability and to establish frameworks for their assessment, similar to the progress already followed for environmental aspects.

In addition, ten general design strategies for incorporating underutilised wood streams into building products, aiming at advancing zero-waste and circularity, were identified: DS.1) Embracing irregularity, DS.2) Design by availability, DS.3) Structural redundancy, DS.4) Stress-aligned optimisation, DS.5) Geometrically efficient forms, DS.6) Homogenisation and standardisation, DS.7) Semi-standardisation, DS.8) Bespoke high-end or experimental solutions, DS.9) Bespoke low-tech solutions, and DS.10) Modification of material properties. Each strategy is associated with distinct implications for the NEB values, highlighting opportunities as well as potential challenges. Their reflection against the NEB Compass demonstrates how design can engage with the various values and needs to advance sustainable, circular, and socially just approaches in construction. These strategies will be further explored in future design work in WP6 and in co-creation in the Living Labs of the WoodStock project. While the review identified applications of underutilised wood streams in many known building component types, there is design potential in developing new, innovative types of products. Looking at opportunities emerging from material properties, technological development and new design approaches identified in WP5 can bring insights for future work.

Overall, the findings point to the need for further research to support broader adoption of underutilised wood streams, not only through standardisation pathways but also through bespoke solutions and inclusive design strategies that respond to diverse social needs. Future work should continue refining these strategies, deepening their integration with the NEB values and working principles, and exploring their broader socio-cultural impacts.

Table 1: Application types across the four underutilised wood streams

Application scale	Application type	LQW	DW	PCRW	HW
1D	Solid beams	×	●	●	●
	I-beams	●	×	×	●
	Glulam	●	●	●	●
	LSL, PSL and LVL	●	×	×	●
	Other beams and columns	●	×	●	×
	Trusses	●	×	●	●
	Structural frames	●	×	×	*
	Door and window frames	×	×	●	●
	Space frames	●	×	×	*
Lattice structures	×	×	●	*	
2D	WBP	●	●	●	●
	Mass timber panels (CLT, DLT, NLT)	●	●	●	●
	Sandwich panels	●	●	×	●
	Other slab systems	●	×	●	●
	Cladding, flooring, decorative panels	●	●	●	●
	Thermal and acoustic insulation	×	●	●	●
	Other façade systems	×	×	●	●
3D	Modular building blocks	×	●	●	×
	Reciprocal and interlocking structures	×	×	●	●
	Shells and gridshell structures	●	×	●	●
	Other free-form structures	×	×	●	●
	Structural connectors	●	×	×	●

Legend: ✕ - application not found, ● - application included in the review, * - applications exist but are not described in detail in the review

3.5 Review of zero-waste building concepts

This report reviewed 103 case studies that demonstrate strategies for using underutilised wood stocks. Each case study was investigated to understand the design process in order to map the strategies used during the design process. The holistic design process presented in this report incorporates the building type, circular design approaches, product selection and the tectonic principles deployed (Fig. 7). Zero-waste strategies are presented in each of the design stages. 10 case studies were selected for further investigation and were assessed with the NEB compass tool. Each case study represents a general concept that instils circular zero-waste solutions for using underutilised wood. The general concepts are not an exhaustive list, but it is envisioned as a first step in showcasing a zero-waste design approach that does so by implementing multiple design strategies holistically.

The review found that by using homogenised and standardised products, zero-waste solutions are easier to deploy. On the other hand, if the construction sector is to adopt varying wood stocks, there is opportunity to investigate solutions that not only use a material that is currently perceived as waste, but the products should also instil circular design approaches to move the solutions from single use to reusable. In doing so, solutions can easily be reused in different locations than first intended, allowing for the timber to remain in use in the built environment. By doing so the sector can switch from the linear “cradle to grave” approach to a circular “cradle-to-cradle” approach.

Figure 7: Four areas of a holistic design approach

3.6 International Survey on wood perception

The WoodStock international survey investigates how regional, demographic, and professional factors shape perceptions and acceptance of reused, recycled, and otherwise underutilised wood resources (Fig. 8). This deliverable summarises the survey’s conception, validation, and translation, marking the completion of the project’s initial methodological phase. Data collection will continue across partner countries throughout the project to build a broader, cross-cultural dataset for subsequent analysis and publication.

The survey contributes to the project by generating evidence on perceived quality, comfort, and contextual suitability of wood products made from underutilised resources. While not replacing structural or regulatory assessments, these insights address a key barrier to uptake: social acceptance of visible wood surfaces in residential settings. This is particularly relevant for multi-storey housing, where acceptance of exposed CLT, hybrid systems, or reclaimed interior components influences the feasibility of timber solutions. By identifying which visual attributes enhance naturalness, beauty, comfort, and “hominess,” and which provoke rejection, the survey informs design decisions that minimise user resistance. As the dataset expands, it will also reveal differences linked to profession, familiarity with wood, and environmental orientation, supporting targeted communication and guiding product suitability across residential, utility, and semi-public contexts.

Participate in the survey here: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/D5W5H23>

Figure 8: Photographs used in the survey

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5. REFERENCES

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